
DEVELOPING AN INSTRUMENT FOR ASSESSING INTERNALIZATION AND ACTUALIZATION OF CULTURAL VALUES FOR JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This study aimed at developing an instrument to assess learners' internalization and actualization on positive cultural values through English as a foreign language learning. Five phases of instructional design proposed by Cennamo dan Kalk (2005) guides this research and development. The five phases comprises: (1) defining (exploring the need from the practical perspective and the theoretical gap), (2) designing (writing the instrument grid design/ table of specification for the instrument), (3) developing (developing the instrument), (4) modelling (discussing the product through forum group discussion and expostulating with expert judgments) and (5) presenting (present the product and testing it to the learners). The technique to analyze the data used factor analysis mainly for exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Factor loading within exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was determined by the number of samples in this research. KMO or Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin was used as the consideration of the sufficiency of the data with the level more than 0,05 ($KMO > 0,05$). Having been processed, the result revealed 0,587 with the significance 0,000. The final results of the study showed that for assessing internalization and actualization of cultural values, there are 25 items with seven factors: deserving the value of achievement, self-confidence, creativities, respectful, discipline, nationalism, and tolerance.

Keywords: culture, internalization, actualization, assessment

1. Introduction

There is a dearth of an instrument to assess learners' understanding or even investigating their level of internalization and actualization toward culture positive values (Berlin, 1992; Díaz-Cabrera, Hernández-Fernaud & Isla-Díaz, 2007; Kiss & Nikolov, 2005; Reiman & Oedewald, 2017), whereas in this digital revolution, positive values are precisely needed. Some studies (Staub, 1979; Park & Peterson, 2006; Martinez & Garcia, 2008; Vauclair, 2009) reported that the level morality of today teenagers ought to be apprehensive. Therefore, realizing the current problem of teenagers' moralities, education should be able to take the real part to help in overcome the problems.

Studies on culture, morality, and developing instruments relates to the issues of positive cultural values are a lot. They are for example Tran 2009; Jensen 2015; Harpham 2017; Kurth and Narvaez 2018; Staines et al. 2019; who intensively investigate the same field. However, an instrument for assessing and observing the learners in Junior high school especially those join an English as a foreign language are still scare.

Meanwhile, a number of studies have proven that through learning language, moralities or positive values can be inculcated (DeRoche and Williams 2001; Piasecka 2016; Mercer and MacIntyre 2014; Talamini et al. 2018;). In addition, an integration of culture values into language learning are a great in quantity (Gay 2010; Gabryś-Barker 2016; Gregersen 2016). This fact is proven

that there are positive responses from language teachers to bring good values to their teaching practices.

Unfortunately, seemingly teachers who have conducted teaching language and integrated positive cultural values do not implement a standard evaluation on monitoring and observing the learners' achievement. Thus, it is assumed that learners' learning outcomes are not standardized and evaluated. Therefore, this paper aims at developing an instrument to assess language learners' internalization and actualization toward positive cultural values. The output of the research is to give a contribution to language teachers who will teach and integrate language and positive cultural values in the classroom.

Explicitly, this paper aims at finding what are the instruments to assess the internalization and actualization of culture values and how are the results of the implementation of the instruments when it is used to assess the internalization and actualization of culture values. Then the objective of this paper is to develop the instruments to assess the internalization and actualization of culture values and to find out the results of the implementation of the instruments when it is used to assess the internalization and actualization of culture values.

2. Literature Review

and Kluckhohn (1952) as cited by Chaer & Agustina (2010: 162) collected a number of culture definitions then make categorization into six characteristic domains. They are: 1) descriptive definition which tends to emphasize culture is built by some elements or sustains. 2) Historical definition that focus on how culture can be inherited or receive socially from generation to generation. 3) Normative definition seeing much deeper on how culture can be understood as the norms and ways of life. 4) Psychological definition tends to understand the role of culture in guiding people as the member of society. In this context, culture plays a role in directing people in adjusting or adapting with their surroundings.

These definitions also give a comprehending the culture as the guidance of society in overcome the problem, even to learn how to live together based on the believed standard. 5) Structural definition stresses culture as a systemic pattern and well regulated. 6) Genetic definition emphasizes on the formation of social standards as the mankind creation. This definition can be interpreted that culture encompasses all the human activities include its whole consequences.

The wide variety of culture definitions are also responded by Kumaravadivelu (2003: 267) and Saifer, Edwards, Ellis, et al. (2011: 9). Their definitions of culture are as follow: Culture is such a complicated concept that it does not lend itself to a single definition or a simple description. It brings to mind different images to different people. In its broadest sense, it includes a wide variety of constructs such as the mental habits, personal prejudices, moral values, social customs, artistic achievements, and aesthetic preferences of particular societies (Kumaravadivelu 2003: 267).

A way of life, especially as it relates to the socially transmitted habits, customs, traditions, and beliefs that characterize a particular group of people at a particular time. It includes the behaviors actions, practices, attitudes, norms, values, communication styles, language, etiquette, spirituality, concepts of health, and healing, beliefs, and institutions of a racial, ethnic, religious, or social group. Culture is the lens through which we look at the world. It is the context within which we operate and make sense of the world (While Saifer, Edwards, Ellis, et al., 2011: 9).

Based on the definitions, it can be understood that culture is structured by many aspects. Kumaravadevelu's rationale can be briefly understood that culture encompasses mental habits, prejudice, moral values, socials custom artistic achieving and aesthetic preference. Those reflect the human behavior, beliefs, and the everyday life of an individual or a group of individuals within a cultural community. While Saifer, Edwards, Ellis, et al., their definition can be comprehended that culture as a broad since it includes a very large aspect in people' lives.

Overall, based on these definitions, culture appertains to some components which are interrelated. Each component implied a certain value which is believed and convinced as the society

guidance to be adopted for the way of life. The values and the norms are categorized into a system that can be found among the society. Since culture is a such of values and norms, automatically it will be kept and preserved from generation to generation.

A broadly sense, culture can be understood as a meaning system which can be taught systematically in education either formal or informal institution. In the long run, culture will be very dynamic when the owners are actively kept and maintained. The effort to introduce a culture to the formal institution will support its existence. Since the meaning system is learnt by the learners so the culture can be transmitted from time to time and from generation to the new generation. By that way, culture gains its function as the guidance to be used by the people for interaction and adaptation in behaving with their surroundings. Koentjaraningrat (1997: 1) through his book entitled *Kebudayaan, Mentalitas dan Pembangunan*, also explains the concept of culture comprises the whole human activities in their life. He points out that the concept of culture can be understood in a broader sense. Culture is a reflection of human mind, their creation and artwork. However, they do not root from their instinct, instead of by means of learning process.

Furthermore, he divides the cultural elements into seven groups, they are: 1) religious system and its ceremonial, 2) system and society organization, 3) knowledge system, 4) language, 5) art, 6) employment system, and 7) technology. The seventh of universal elements would still be split into the narrower or sub-elements. Since religious system and its ceremonial are at the highest level, seemingly, it is the most difficult culture component that can be affected. There are, however, some possibilities to change for religious equipment or technology. It is in line with the development of technology in community. On the contrary, cultural elements such as art, employment system, and technology will be very easy to be affected. It depends on how strong the religious or dogma kept or believed by the community.

Since culture is the set of practices, codes and values (Richard & Schmidt, 2002: 138) thus it can be categorized into its group. Koentjaraningrat, (1997: 5-6) briefly codes culture realization into three groups, they are: 1) idea (ideel), 2) social system, and 3) physical culture. Related to the term *idea* as the first realization, it can be interpreted as an abstract concept. Another term of this concept is norm, mores, or local custom. Since the term "idea" is very abstract, sometime it can be easily observed by understanding their way of thinking and behavior norms. Courteousness is one of the most real example of culture realization which deals with idea parameter.

Then, in line with the term of social system as the second culture realization, it deals with how people doing an interaction among others. The social system emphasizes on how people as the member of society internalize and actualize the believed norm in their daily life. This second culture realization tends to be more tangible. Sometime it is stated of being felt, having monetary value, real and substantial. The examples to illustrate this culture realization are mutual assistance or *Gotong Royong*, visiting a sick friend, lowering the voice when making a conversation with older people, bowing when talking with older people, talking politely, nicely and courteously and there are many examples that we can find in our surrounding.

The third culture realization is physical culture. It is supposed to be the most concrete culture that we can observe in the middle of society. Since it is physical features as the results of human activity and creativity, these kinds of cultural manifestations are considered to be much more visible. The examples that can be found are temples, mosque, church which are followed by some objects for worship. And then, things related to weapons can also be found such as swords, shields, arrows, wavy double-bladed dagger. We can find a wide range of physical cultural manifestations around us. Other examples that we can find are agricultural equipment, such as hoes, plows, sickles, and so forth. In addition, this manifestation is shaped in the traditional games, traditional food and traditional dances that is usually held in several events such as wedding ceremonies or/and in other formal occasions.

Those of cultural manifestations such as idea (ideel), social system, custom, physical cultural manifestation definitely can never be separated from each other. In a greater detail, Koentjaraningrat

(1997: 6) figures out that the *ideel* culture and custom control as well as giving a direction toward the human behaviors include their creations. This notion encounters a very large scope such as people's ways of thinking, their ideas, and their daily life actions and their creation such as the fine art, traditional dance, agriculture tool as well as their traditional houses to support their agriculture activities. Those are the human creation as the realization of physical culture.

The first manifestation provides the rules that can be used as a guideline in social life. Its functions are to give a direction to the society in determent the personification in concrete form of their deeds. The following is a summary of the concept, and the embodiment or concrete manifestation of the cultural elements which have been illustrated in the form of charts by the researcher sourced from Koentjaraningrat (1997: 1-8).

Dewantara (1994) as cited by Susatya (2010: 29) states that people who do not touched by culture, they are still a natural and they need to be trained and educated to know how their own culture in order to have a cultural sensibility. As a matter of fact, the personality of natural people, there are high ego and lack of empathy feeling toward their surroundings. Whereas the one who has known well their culture will be more mature or reach full of their maturity. It is in line with Peursen's concept (1988) in Susatya (2010: 29) that the characteristics of cultural people, they are able to teach themselves to which is good and which one is not good. Saravanan (1995) in Bao Dat (2008: 263) likewise believed that when the children were consistently taught to behave in ways of cultural mores and aspiration of their communities, not only would they have meaningful contributions but also able to consolidate their self-esteem and cultural identity to the society.

In line with the idea, Alwasilah (2003: 71) highlights that there are at least two reasons why Indonesian cultures or local cultures need to be preserved. "They constitute national heritage, by which a nation is identified and respected by other people, and they constitute a drawing card for peoples from other parts of the world". However, Bransford, Brown, & Cocking (2000: 49) state that instruction should enable learners to see models of how experts organize and solve problems that will be helpful and then the level of complexity of the materials designed must be tailored to the learners' condition and current level of knowledge and skills.

Moreover, Bao Dat (2008: 270) highlights that some studies in the region point out that learners preferred to flexible materials which give them to share and discuss the issue of cultural values. Regarding to the culture-based English instructional materials, the researcher as a material designer referred to the latest curriculum. It is in line with Byrd' idea (2001: 416) that there are three issues must be considered in instructional materials which form in the textbook: 1) curriculum, 2) learners, and 3) teachers. These can be understood that when developing the materials, the three components must be reasonably accommodated in it. The curriculum as the operational guideline must be the first pinpoint. Then for learners, since the materials are dedicated for them thus it must meet to their needs. In order to achieve the goal, materials should be made up by the three elements: content, example, and exercise. Afterwards, it should be evaluated whether the implementation of such instructional materials will be effective to support English teaching and learning process or not.

The Notion of Cultural Values and Language Teaching

Dealing with the education context, indeed there are many ways that can be done to bring culture values into teaching and learning activities. It is for example through integrating culture through teaching material and some learning activities. Therefore, to preserve the positives culture, education has a great role. However, it is needed an instrument to be used to assess how far the students can understand the culture values taught in their class.

With regard to culture, teaching by the help of culture values will foster learners' wisdom sensibility. As Rahyono (2009: 8) states in his book that local wisdoms are comprehensive, keenness and cleverness created based on the people 'experiences until those are possessed together. Since the local wisdom contained a very precious value, it will not be excessive if those are taught interactively in subject matter organized in education system.

In line with the previous arguments, the researcher thinks that developing an instrument to assess the internalization and actualization of culture values would be very helpful. In addition, teaching with the help of culture-based initiated by a research and developed with a certain procedure would meet the learners' needs. Furthermore, those also could be used to support internalizing and actualizing of positives values.

Having discussed the culture based on the theoretical perspective, this research attempts to develop the instrument to assess the internalization and actualization of culture values through teaching and learning activities. It is necessary to do because teacher can control and observe the learners' understanding of culture values.

3. Resarch Methods

was appropriate to implement. Then the model that was used as the guideline in developing the instrument was model proposed by Cennamo dan Kalk (2005) consisting of five phases. They were comprises: (1) defining (exploring the need from the practical perspective and the theoretical gap), (2) designing (writing the instrument grid design/ table of specification for the instrument), (3) developing (developing the instrument), (4) modelling (discussing the product through forum group discussion and expostulating with expert judgments) and (5) presenting (present the product and testing it to the learners). The subject of the research was the learners of Junior High School in Yogyakarta while the sample of the research is four schools from four districts. There are 154 learners from four schools who awere involved in the research. They are State Junior High Schools of Yogyakarta.

Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

The techniques to collect the data in this research are to use non-test or it is called questionnaire. The questionnaires used in this research are to evaluate the learners' level of internalization and actualization toward culture values, and the questionnaires are developed based on the table of specification. The questionnaires are developed by using Likert scale type.

Data Analysis Techniques

The technique to analyze the data will use factor analysis mainly for exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Factor loading within exploratory factor analysis (EFA) will be determined by the number of samples in this research. KMO or Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin is used as the consideration of the sufficiency of the data with the level more than 0,05 ($KMO > 0,05$).

4. Results and Discussion

Designing the Table of Specification for the Instrument

In designing the instrument for assessing the internalization and actualization levels of Junior High School Students' positive culture values, the researcher made the following guideline.

A. Conceptual definition

- Culture is a dynamic, explicit and implicit rule system that has been built by a group of people with the aim of ensuring their survival. Culture encompasses the attitudes, values, beliefs, norms and behaviors that are shared by a group of concerned people and are passed down across generations.
- Cultural values are the soul and basis of all forms of culture. The order of life of community activities is a concrete reflected on their cultural values.

B. Operational definition

- Cultural values that will be measured in the process of internalization and actualization of students are behaviors that are in accordance with the goals and strategies of national development and lead to the realization of a distinctive civilization based on the philosophy and outlook of the developing Indonesian nation.

C. Indicator of national cultural values referred to this questionnaire include:

- Appreciating Achievements: a. trying to get the best results, and b. use the opportunity given by the teacher as well as possible.
- Confidence: a. dare to express an opinion. b. dare to appear in front of the class.
- Creative: Able to find new solutions to a problem.
- Sincerely: a. Listen to the teacher when explaining., b. Speak politely to both the teacher and friends, and c. Don't interrupt when the conversation.
- Discipline: a. Use your time as well as possible., b. Can be a role model, c. Maintain the school environment, d. Orderly and obedient to regulations.
- Nationalism: a. Get to know the name of a national hero. b. Proud to be an Indonesian society.
- Tolerance, a. Appreciate differences of opinion. b. Respect differences in cultural values of other communities.

The Interpretation of Exploratory Factor Analysis

There were 25 items in the questionnaires to measure internalizing and actualizing of culture values. They were deserved to be valid since those were validated both from the content and construct validity. To reveal the content validity, the questionnaires were developed based on the table of specification, whereas to maintain the construct validity, they were discussed to the expert judgment (those whose expertise are well recognized) and then were tested in the tryout to find the empirical evidence.

To determine the empirical data, the questionnaires were analyzed by using statistical analysis particularly for factor analysis. It was aimed at knowing any kind of factors supported the measurement to learners' affective domain. There were eleven factors stated in the 1st draft with 40 indicators of the prepared instrument. However, after they had been discussed to the thesis consultant, there were some that ought to be omitted.

After the questionnaires were decided to be fixed then they were tested to the population in four Junior High Schools. IBM SPSS Statistics Data Editor (*Statistical Package for Social Science*) 20.0 for Windows especially by using KMO and Bartlett's Test was applied to analysis the instruments.

The use KMO and Bartlett's Test was aimed at making sure whether all of the factors which had been prepared and designed in the questionnaires were representative. Later on, several weeks before the questionnaires were used in the tryout, its result of KMO and Bartlett's Test had been acquired. The extraction of analytical factor analysis was presented on the following table 1.

Table 1.

The Result of KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.587
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1464.240
	df	435
	Sig.	.000

Having process the data by using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy, the result revealed 0,587 with the significance 0,000. Since the final result proceed by Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy reached more than 0,5 ($p > 0,5$) furthermore the researcher proceeds to the next calculation by considering and omitting the lower score. In a final manner, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy recommended the final score by omitting some components into six components. The entirety of statistical analysis mainly using KMO and Bartlett's, were enclosed in this paper.

Result of Culture Values Questionnaire Validity

Based on the consideration from the statistical computation, the result of test validity and reliability of the research instruments were deserved to be valid and reliable. Items validity was aimed at making sure the appropriateness and usefulness of the instruments thus reliability was aimed at finding out the test's consistency and stability. Having found their statistical calculation, and they had been proven to be valid and reliable then they could be used to gain the expected data and the result of the final data analysis of the research could be generalized as a whole.

Result of Culture Values Questionnaire Reliability

Alpha Cronbach formula was applied to find out the reliability of the instruments. It was aimed at measuring the reliability of the questionnaires for items. The calculation used the IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 *for Windows*. The result of test Reliability was stated of being reliable because the percentage reached 0.871. It was exactly higher than 0.7. Based on the assumption of the *Alpha Cronbach* coefficient, it ought to be higher than 0.7. The data calculation could be seen on the following table 2.

Table 2. Reliability Statistics Analysis of Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.871	30

Based on the consideration from the statistical computation, the result of test validity and reliability of the research instruments were deserved to be valid and reliable. Items validity was aimed at making sure the appropriateness and usefulness of the instruments thus reliability was aimed at finding out the test's consistency and stability. Having found their statistical calculation, and they had been proven to be valid and reliable then they could be used to gain the expected data and the result of the final data analysis of the research could be generalized as a whole.

The result of Instruments Implementation

To know the quality of the instrument, they were tested to the learners to know their level of internalization and actualization of culture values. The questionnaire utilized in that objective consisted of 25 items with four scales. The questionnaire consisted of seven factors. They were: (1) deserving the value of achievement, (2) self-confidence, (3) creativities, (4) respectful, (5) discipline, (6) nationalism, and (7) tolerance.

The measurement instruments used Likert scale with the option of favorable as the positive respond and unfavorable as the negative respond. The description of the respond comprised: **4.** indicated constantly, **3.** indicated frequently, **2.** indicated infrequently, and **1.** indicated never. The description of each category encompassed the maximum score which was around 100 until 25 as the minimum score. The students would be judged to have a very good understanding and manner of acting when their score reached 78 until 100. When they got 63 until 77 signed that they had a good understanding and manner of acting, while when the score was less than 62 indicated that the students needed an intensive guidance. The following data showed the summary of statistical descriptive.

Table 4. Statistical Descriptive of Cultural Values Internalization and Actualization

Criteria	Descriptions	Frequency (Students)	Percent
A	Very Good	32	47.1%
B	Good	36	52.9%
C	Fair	0	0
Total		68	100%

Chart 1. Students' Internalization and Actualization of Cultural Value

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

To develop the instruments to assess the internalization and actualization of culture values, model proposed by Cinnamon dan Kalk (2005) was adopted in this research and development. There were five phases in adopting their model. They were guiding this research and development. The five phases comprises: (1) defining (exploring the need from the practical perspective and the theoretical gap), (2) designing (writing the instrument grid design/ table of specification for the instrument), (3) developing (developing the instrument), (4) modelling (discussing the product through forum group discussion and expostulating with expert judgments) and (5) presenting (present the product and testing it to the learners).

The technique to analyze the data used factor analysis mainly for exploratory factor analysis (EFA). Factor loading within exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was determined by the number of samples in this research. KMO or Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin was used as the consideration of the sufficiency of the data with the level more than 0,05 ($KMO > 0,05$). Having been processed, the result revealed 0,587 with the significance 0,000. The final results of the study showed that for assessing internalization and actualization of cultural values, there are 25 items with seven factors: deserving the value of achievement, self-confidence, creativities, respectful, discipline, nationalism, and tolerance.

Based on the research and development that has been done, to assess the level of internalization and actualization of positive cultural values for learners, this product of the research can be utilized. By using this instrument, at least the teachers will be helped and can map the learners' level of progress, especially related to their domain of affection. However, there are a number of things that need to be considered related to the results of this first study (1) the context or background of the learner will also influence the questionnaire used, and (2) the learning material to be used also has an influence. That is, this questionnaire is only intended for teachers who will assess the attitude of students in English classes.

8. About the Author(s)

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